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9 ЖИЛД, 1 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 1

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 1

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ISSN: 2181-9904

www.tadqiqot.uz

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

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MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED BY STREPTOZOTOCIN

For citation: Tilyabov Ikram, Usmanov Ravshan. Morphological changes of the kidneys of rats in diabetes induced by streptozotocin. Journal of biomedicine and practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 1, pp.448-457

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10940019>

ABSTRACT

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM), more often type 2, is found in children. Although advanced hyperglycemic nephropathies (GN), such as loss of nephron filtration rate (NFT), do not occur until adulthood, renal biopsies show structural GN within 1.5–5 years after initiation of type 1 QD. shows changes. The earliest clinical sign of GN, such as increased urinary albumin excretion, usually appears in childhood and adolescence and is an important opportunity for early GN detection and treatment. Research in type 1 diabetes has shown that GN is characteristic of a subset of people with diabetes who are at high risk of premature death, which increases the focus on detection, prevention, and treatment of GN. Preliminary studies suggest that youth-onset type 2 diabetes is associated with a higher prevalence of risk factors. Research will help to better understand the risk factors, underlying mechanisms, and treatment options for GN in youth-onset type 2 diabetes.

Key words: morphology, morometry, kidney, ball, hyperglycemic nephropathies, atrophy, sclerosis, diabetes mellitus with streptothiazine.

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МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ПОЧЕК КРЫС ПРИ ДИАБЕТЕ, ИНДУЦИРОВАННОМ СТРЕПТОЗОТОКИНОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

У детей встречается сахарный диабет (СД) 1-го типа, чаще 2-го типа. Хотя прогрессирующие гипергликемические нефропатии (ГН), такие как снижение скорости фильтрации нефронов (СФН), не возникают до взрослой жизни, биопсия почек показывает структурный ГН в течение

1,5–5 лет после начала КТ 1 типа. Самые ранние клинические признаки ГН, такие как повышенная экскреция альбумина с мочой, обычно появляются в детстве и подростковом возрасте и представляют собой важную возможность для раннего выявления и лечения ГН. Исследования диабета 1 типа показали, что ГН характерен для подгруппы людей с диабетом, которые подвергаются высокому риску преждевременной смерти, что увеличивает внимание к выявлению, профилактике и лечению ГН. Предварительные исследования показывают, что диабет 2 типа, возникший в молодом возрасте, связан с более высокой распространенностью факторов риска. Исследования помогут лучше понять факторы риска, основные механизмы и варианты лечения ГН при диабете 2 типа у молодых людей.

Ключевые слова: морфология, морометрия, почка, шарик, гипергликемические нефропатии, атрофия, склероз, сахарный диабет со стрептоптиазинном.

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STREPTOZOTOTSIN ORQALI KELIB CHIQQAN QANDLI DIABETDA KALAMUSH AVLODLARI BUYRAKLARNING MORFOLOGIK O'ZGARISHLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Bolalarda, odatda, Qandi diabet(QD)ning 1-turi, ko'proq 2-turi uchramoqda. Rivojlangan giperglikemik nefropatiyalar (GN), masalan, nefronda filtratsiya tezligi (NFT) yo'qolishi, balog'at yoshiga qadar sodir bo'lmasa -da, buyrak biopsiyalari 1-turdagi QD boshlanganidan keyin 1,5-5 yil ichida GN tarkibiy o'zgarishlarini ko'rsatadi. GNning eng erta klinik belgisi, masalan, siydikda albumin ajralishining ko'payishi, odatda bolalik va o'smirlilik davrida paydo bo'ladi va erta GNni aniqlash va davolash uchun muhim imkoniyatdir. 1-turdagi diabet masalasida olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, GN erta o'lim xavfi yuqori bo'lgan diabet bilan og'rig'an odamlarning bir qismiga xos, bu GNni aniqlash, oldini olish va davolashga etiborni kuchaytiradi. Dastlabki tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yoshlarda boshlangan 2-turdagi QD xavf omillarining tarqalishi yuqoriligi bilan bog'liq. Yoshlarda boshlangan 2-turdagi QDda GN uchun xavf omillarini, asosiy mexanizmlarini va davolash variantlarni chuqurroq tushunib olish borasida ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: morfologiya, morometriya, buyrak, koptokcha, giperglikemik nefropatiyalar, atrofiya, skleroz, streptotsiazinli qandli diabet.

Mavzuning dolzarbliligi: QD bolalar va o'smirlar orasida keng tarqalgan surunkali kasalliklardan biri. Hozirda AQShda 20 yoshdan kichik 190 000 dan ortiq QD bilan kasallangan odamlar bor [1] va bu raqam 2050 yilga borib ikki baravar yoki undan ko'proq o'sishi bashorat qilinmoqda [2]. 1-turdagi QD bolalar va o'smirlardagi kasalliklarning asosiy shakli bo'lib kelgan. Biroq, so'nggi yigirma yil ichida bolalarda semirishning ko'payishi bolalar va o'smirlar orasida 2-turdagi QD bilan kasallanishning ko'payishiga olib keldi [1].

QD, asosan, uzoq muddatli asoratlari natijasida o'limga olib kelishi sezilarli darajada oshishi uzoq vaqtdan ma'lum. 1-turdagi [3, 4] va 2-turdagi [5] QDga chalinganlarda buyrak kasalliklari rivojlanadi. Ushbu kuzatishlar GN o'lim xavfi yuqori bo'lgan populyatsiya belgisi sifatida va, ehtimol, ortiqcha o'limga bevosita hissa qo'shadigan xavf omili sifatida muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. GNning yanada og'ir bosqichlari rivojlanishi uchun o'nlab yillar kerak, shuning uchun bolalikda kamdan-kam kuzatilsa-da, buyrak biopsiyalari diabet boshlanganidan keyin 1,5-5 yil o'tgach, kattalar va bolalarda GNga xos bo'lgan tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni ko'rsatadi [6-7]. Bu shundan dalolat beradiki, GN diabet boshlanganidan keyin tez orada yuzaga keladi va bu qisqa interval kasallik kechishini aniqlash va terapevtik aralashuvlarni amalga oshirish uchun juda muhim, bu,

o'z navbatida, bolalar va o'smirlardagi xavf omillarini jadal va doimiy monitoring qilishni taqozo qiladi. Ehtimol, kattalarnikidan ko'ra, bolalar va o'smirlarda GNni erta tashxislash uchun mavjud vositalarimiz kamdir. Bolalardagi QDning bola hayotining kechishiga og'ir ta'siri bor ekanki, bu bizni barcha mavjud vositalar va resurslardan to'liq foydalanishni, ularning kuchli tomonlari va cheklovlarini chuqur tushunishni, shuningdek, yangi diagnostika vositalari va davolash usullarini ishlab chiqish borasida ilmiy tadqiqotlarni amalga oshirishni talab qiladi.

1-turdagi QD bilan solishtirganda uning umumiy tarqalishi kam bo'lishiga qaramay, yoshlarda 2-turdagi QDning ko'payishi to'rtta sababga ko'ra jiddiy sog'liqni saqlash muammosini keltirib chiqaradi: 2-turdagi QDga chalingan yoshlar diabetik asoratlar va o'lim uchun xavf omillarining ko'proq tarqalishiga ega. Ushbu xavf omillarini nazorat qilishning yomonligi, asoratlarning tezroq rivojlanishini, o'limning yuqori ko'rsatkichlarini va eng dahshatlisi, xavf omillarini nazorat qilishga urinishlarga qaramay, asoratlarning to'xtovsiz rivojlanishini ko'rsatadi.

Patologiyada buyrak to'qimalarining holatini o'rganish va kasallikning borishini bashorat qilishning muhim usuli buyrak biopsiyasi namunalarini morfologik o'rganishdir. Kasalliklarni eksperimental modellashtirishda nefronlarning turli bo'limlaridagi strukturaviy va ultrastrukturali muntazam o'zgarishlarni tahlil qilish zamonaviy nefrologiyaning eng muhim muammolaridan biridir. Hozirgi vaqtda mavjud adabiyotlarda biz tajribada eng ko'p ishlatiladigan laboratoriya (chiziqli bo'lmagan) oq kalamushlar buyraklarining normal morfometrik parametrlarini baholash uchun yagona kontseptsiyani topmadik. Buyrak patologiyasini modellashtirishda mualliflar baholash uchun makroskopik, funktsional, biokimyoviy ko'rsatkichlardan foydalanadilar, faqat bir nechtasi o'z ishlarida nefron parametrlaridagi morfometrik o'zgarishlarni baholaydi.

Maqsad Streptozotsinli qandli diabet bilan kasallangan kalamushlarning avlodlarida buyrak nefronlarining morfologik o'zgarishlarini o'rganish.

Materiallar va usullar Tadqiqot uchun laboratoriya oq kalamushlari ishlatilgan:

3 kunlik 68.4gr±2.31gr

10 kunlik 79.74gr±2.61gr

30 kunlik 106.5gr±2.7gr,

60 kunlik 122.5gr±2.7gr,

90kunlik 153.6gr±3.7gr bo'lgan 60ta bo'lgan oq kalmush bolalari olindi . Hayvonlar

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasida standart vivarium sharoitida, har bir katakda 10 tadan ko'p bo'lmagan yog'och talaslari bo'lgan plastik qafaslarda saqlangan. Vivariumning dietasi va ichish rejimi standartdir.

Oldimizga qo'yilgan maqsadga erishish, hamda vazifalarni bajarish uchun tadqiqotning ob'ekti sifatida postnatal davrlarida bo'lgan 60 ta Vistar zotiga mansub oq laborator kalamushlardan foydalanildi. Kalamushlar 2 ta guruhga ajratildi. Birinchi guruhni tajriba guruhi tashkil etdi. Tajriba guruhida homildor oq laborator kalamushlariga Sitrat tamponida (Citratebuffersolution, 0,09M, Sigma) streptozotsinni (Streptozocin, Sigma) 40 mg/kg dozada, inektsiya hajmi 0,5 ml bo'lgan bir marta qorin bo'shlig'iga yuborish orqali qandli diabetning tajribaviy modelini chaqirildi. Ikkinchi guruh nazorat guruhi bo'lib, bunda kalamushlarning qorin bo'shlig'iga 0,9 % li fiziologik eritma yuborildi. Nazorat va tajriba guruhidagi kalamushlardan davriy ravishda reja asosida dum venasidan qon olinib qon va siydikdagi glyukoza darajasini avtomatik biokimyoviy va ferment immunoassay analizatorida tahlil qilamiz. Kalamushlar postnatal ontogeneznining turli davrlarida dekapitatsiya usulida jonsizlantirildi. Postnatal ontogeneznining quyidagi muddatlarida: 3-10-30-60-90-kunliklarida ontogenezni davrlarida o'rgandik.

Natijalar va muhokama

Shumlyanskiy-Boumen Kapsulaning parietal varag'ining qalinligi mkmda

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	0,375092	0,075533	0,364167
2	10	0,400583	0,080667	0,364167
3	30	0,40204	0,08096	0,437
4	60	0,37582	0,07568	0,437

5	90	0,35834	0,07216	0,437
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Kapsulaning parietal varag'ining qalinligining 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Shumlyanskiy-Boumen kapsulasi bilan glomerulus maydoni, mkm²da

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	4630,537	720,3992	4495,667
2	10	4945,233	769,3583	4495,667
3	30	4963,216	772,156	5394,8
4	60	4639,528	721,798	5394,8
5	90	4423,736	688,226	5394,8

kapsulasi bilan glomerulus maydoni 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Siydik bo'shlig'ining maydoni, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	1343,807	295,3525	1304,667

2	10	1435,133	315,425	1304,667
3	30	1440,352	316,572	1565,6
4	60	1346,416	295,926	1565,6
5	90	1283,792	282,162	1565,6

Siydik bo'shlig'ining maydoni, mkm²
3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Koptokcha kapillyarlarining maydoni, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	3323,553	501,2667	3226,75
2	10	3549,425	535,3333	3226,75
3	30	3562,332	537,28	3872,1
4	60	3330,006	502,24	3872,1
5	90	3175,122	478,88	3872,1

Koptokcha kapillyarlarining maydoni, mkm²
3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

OQ KALMUSH BUYRAKARINING DISTAL KANALCHALAR O'LCHAMLARI

Distal kanalchalar diametr, mkm

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	18,47133	2,738083	17,93333
2	10	19,72667	2,924167	17,93333
3	30	19,7984	2,9348	21,52
4	60	18,5072	2,7434	21,52
5	90	17,6464	2,6158	21,52

Distal kanalchalar diametrining mkmda 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Distal kanalchalar Lyumenar membranasi maydoni, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	10,918	1,733833	10,6
2	10	11,66	1,851667	10,6
3	30	11,7024	1,8584	12,72
4	60	10,9392	1,7372	12,72
5	90	10,4304	1,6564	12,72

Distal kanalchalarning Lyumenar membranasi maydoni, mkm²da 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Distal kanalchalar primetr, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	69,35333	8,119833	67,33333
2	10	74,06667	8,671667	67,33333
3	30	74,336	8,7032	80,8
4	60	69,488	8,1356	80,8
5	90	66,256	7,7572	80,8

Distal kanalchalarning primetr, mkm²da 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Distal kanalchalar maydoni, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	341,5394	58,02333	331,5917
2	10	364,7508	61,96667	331,5917
3	30	366,0772	62,192	397,91
4	60	342,2026	58,136	397,91
5	90	326,2862	55,432	397,91

Distal kanalchalarning maydoni, mkm²da 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

OQ KALMUSH BUYRAKARINING PROKSIMAL KANALCHALAR O'LCHAMLARI

Proksimal kanalchalar diametr, mkm

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	30,49658	5,519083	29,60833
2	10	32,56917	5,894167	29,60833
3	30	32,6876	5,9156	35,53
4	60	30,5558	5,5298	35,53
5	90	29,1346	5,2726	35,53

Proksimal kanalchalar diametrining mkm da 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Proksimal kanalchalarning Lyumenar membranasi maydoni, mkm²da

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	15,67317	5,58775	15,21667
2	10	16,73833	5,9675	15,21667
3	30	16,7992	5,9892	18,26
4	60	15,7036	5,5986	18,26
5	90	14,9732	5,3382	18,26

Proksimal kanalchalarning Lyumenar membranasi maydoni, mkm²da 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatgichlarining taqqoslanishi

Proksimal kanalchalarning primetr, mkm²

	Kunlari	Qiymat (M ± m)		Norma
1	3	112,1069	32,84842	108,8417
2	10	119,7258	35,08083	108,8417
3	30	120,1612	35,2084	130,61
4	60	112,3246	32,9122	130,61
5	90	107,1002	31,3814	130,61

Proksimal kanalchalarning primetr, mkm² 3-10-30-60-90-kunlarda normal va patologik ko'rsatkichlarining taqqoslanishi

Xulosa: Morfometrik tadqiqotlar natijalari ko'rsatishicha, Shumlyanskiy-Boumen kapsulasining parietal varag'i qalinligi, buyrak ko'ptokchasi maydoni, buyrak tanasidagi siydik bo'shlig'ining maydoni, buyrak ko'ptokchasi kapillyar to'ri maydoni kabi ko'rsatkichlarda jiddiy o'zgarishlar aniqlandi. Jumladan, eksperiment muddatlari ortib borgani sari Shumlyanskiy-Boumen kapsulasining parietal varag'i qalinligi (tajribaning 3-kunidagi 0,375092-0,075533 mkmga solishtirganda 0,35834-0,07216 mkmga), buyrak ko'ptokchasi maydoni (tajribaning 3-kunidagi 4630,537-720,3992 mkm²ga solishtirganda 4423,736-688,226 mkm²ga), buyrak tanasidagi siydik bo'shlig'ining maydoni (tajribaning 3-kunidagi 1343,807-295,3525 mkm²ga solishtirganda 1283,792-282,162mkm²ga), buyrak ko'ptokchasi kapillyar to'ri maydoni (tajribaning 3-kunidagi 3323,553-501,2667 mkm²ga solishtirganda 3175,122-478,88 mkm²ga) kamayganligi qayd qilindi. Bu buyrak to'qimalarida sklerotik o'zgarishlar rivojlanishi va kuchayib borishidan dalolat beradi, natijada buyraklarning funktsional holatida chuqur buzilishlar yuzaga keladi.

Shunday qilib, ona kalamushlarda streptozotsin ta'siri ostida chaqirilgan QD oqibatida ushbu kalamushlardan tug'ilgan avlodlarning buyraklarida sezilarli darajadagi morfologik va funktsional o'zgarishlar yuz beradi. Bu o'zgarishlar kalamush bolalari hayotining 90-kunigacha davom etadi. Eksperimental tadqiqot davomida olingan ilmiy ma'lumotlar onadagi QD sharoitida vujudga kelgan bolalar buyraklarining postnatal ontogenezi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini skrining jarayonida o'rganish uchun asos bo'la oladi.

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Статья поступила в редакцию 07.01.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 20.02.2024; принята к публикации 24.02.2024.

The article was submitted 07.01.2024; approved after reviewing 20.02.2024; accepted for publication 24.02.2024

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Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Тиябов Икрам — идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи;

Усманов Равшан — сбор и анализ литературных источников, написание текста.

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Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Tilyabov Ikrom — ideological concept of the work, writing the text; editing the article;

Usmanov Ravshan — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

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JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 1

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